

Proof & Reformulating of Collatz conjecture

Eman Hamad

Bentmasr266@gmail.com

Abstract

The Collatz's conjecture is an unsolved problem in mathematics. It is named after Lothar Collatz in 1973. The conjecture also known as Syracuse conjecture or problem. Take any positive integer n . If n is even then divide it by 2, else do "triple plus one" and get $3n + 1$. The conjecture is that for all numbers, this process converges to one. In this paper, In the first part, we discuss every positive natural number goes through a number n of steps. This number is equivalent to 2^n in the same row. If we prove that all positive natural numbers, by applying the multiplication steps in Collatz reach to 2^n , and then by applying division, we reach $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$, this is considered proof of the Collatz conjecture By applying the law $6^m N + E = 2^n$. In the second part, we combine the two steps of Collatz and reformulate the conjecture.

1-Introduction.

The Collatz conjecture is an unsolved problem in mathematics. It is named after Lothar Collatz in 1973. The conjecture also known as Syracuse conjecture Although the problem on which the conjecture is built is remarkably simple to explain and understand, the nature of the conjecture makes proving or disproving the conjecture exceedingly difficult.

In directed graph odd number is equivalent to double the input.

$$n \equiv 2(3n+1) \qquad n \equiv 6n+2$$

even number is a multiple of an odd number.

$$\begin{array}{cccc} 5 \equiv 32 & 10 \equiv 64 & 20 \equiv 128 & 40 \equiv 256 \\ n \equiv 6n+2 & 2n \equiv 6n+(2 \times 2) & 4n \equiv 6n+(2 \times 4) & 8n \equiv 6n+(2 \times 8) \end{array}$$

If $(2^n N)$ is even number, where N is an odd number.

$$2^n N \equiv 6 \times (2^n N) + (2 \times 2^n)$$

In this way we keep getting the number's equivalences until we reach 2^n

2- Number of steps in Collatz.

$n \equiv 6n+2$ for odd number, $2^n N \equiv 6 \times (2^n N) + (2 \times 2^n)$ for even number.

Example 2.1 $n=13$ $(13 \times 6) + 2 = 80$ $80 = 16 \times 5$

$$(80 \times 6) + (2 \times 16) = 512 = 2^9$$

This number goes through 9 steps.

Example 2.2 $n=7$ $(7 \times 6) + 2 = 44$ $44 = 4 \times 11$

$$(44 \times 6) + (2 \times 4) = 272 \quad 272 = 16 \times 17$$

$$(272 \times 6) + (2 \times 16) = 1664 \quad 1664 = 128 \times 13$$

$$(1664 \times 6) + (2 \times 128) = 10240 \quad 10240 = 2048 \times 5$$

$$(10240 \times 6) + (2 \times 2048) = 65536 = 2^{16}$$

This number is going through 16 steps

3- the high number reach.

To know the high number reaches, We choose the highest odd number that the number passes through and take its input.

In the previous Example 2.2 number 7 goes through (7,11,17,13,5) the highest odd number is 17

Its input $(3 \times 17) + 1 = 52$ $\therefore 52$ is the high number reach.

If the even number itself is greater than the high number reaches, the even number itself is the highest number reached by the number.

Example 3.1 $n=48$ $48 = 16 \times 3$ $(48 \times 6) + (2 \times 16) = 320$

$320 = 64 \times 5$ $(320 \times 6) + (2 \times 64) = 2048 = 2^{11}$

This number is going through 11 steps.

This number goes through (3,5) the highest odd number is 5,

Its input $(3 \times 5) + 1 = 16$, $48 > 16$ $\therefore 48$ is the high number reach.

4- Proof of Collatz conjecture.

$$(3n+1) \times 2 \quad (6n+2)$$

for odd number $N \equiv 6N+2$

for even number $N \equiv 6N+2 \times 2^n$

When these steps are repeated several times, we obtain the equivalent numbers of the number (multiples of the odd numbers that the number passes through), up to 2^n .

$$6N+2$$

$$6(6N+2)+2^n$$

$$6(6(6N+2)+2^n)+2^n$$

$$[6(6(6(6(6N+2)+2^n)+2^n)+2^n+2^n)] \quad \text{several times}$$

$$6^m N + E = 2^n$$

Where m The number of chains that are far from the main axis or the number of multiplication stages in Collatz.

N odd number or even number.

E is A constant even number for each number.

n step number.

$$d = n - m$$

d division number

We can also locate the number in directed graph.

Then $(\frac{2^n}{2})$ n times

Each number has its own even number E from which it begins to ascend until it reaches 2^n . This number depends on its position in the row and how close or far it is from the main axis.

Example4.1

$N=17$

$$\{6[6(6N+2)+2 \times 8]+2 \times 128\}=6[(36N+2)+16]+256$$

$$=216N+168+256=(216N+424)=4096=2^{12}$$

$$6^3 \times 17+424=2^{12}$$

$$n=12$$

$$m=3$$

$$d=n-m=12-3=9$$

$$E=424$$

This number is going through a 12 step, It has 3 steps of multiplication and 9 steps of division. This number is equivalent to 2^{12} in the same row and is 3 chains away from the main axis (2^n).

Example4.2 N=53

$$[6(6N+2)+2 \times 64]=36N+12+128=36+140=2048=2^{11}$$

$$6^2 \times 53+140=2^{11}$$

$$n=11$$

$$m=2$$

$$d=n-m=11-2=9$$

$$E=140$$

This number is going through a 11 step, It has 2 steps of multiplication and 9 steps of division. This number is equivalent to 2^{11} in same row and is 2 chains away from the main axis (2^n).

5-formulate the Collatz equation.

When the number is even, we divide it by 2, and when it is odd, we multiply it by 3 and add 1 (to get an even number again). So the next step after multiplication and addition is always division, to get approximately $3/2$ of the value of the odd number. Therefore, we can combine the two steps to know what this value represents.

The number 1 is the first odd number to which we add 1 as well. The number 3 is the second odd number to which we add 2. The number 5 is the third odd number to which we add 3. The number 7 is the fourth odd number to which we add 4. The number 9 is the fifth odd number to which we add 5. And so on in the same order of the odd numbers.

We can formulate the Collatz equation in this form:

Theory5.1 (If we have an odd number, we add its order among the odd numbers, and if we have an even number, we divide it by 2. We repeat this process several times to finally get $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$).

If we want to know the order of an odd number (n) among the odd numbers, we add one to this number and then divide it by 2.

$$\frac{n+1}{2}$$

We can also create a Collatz equation that combines the steps of multiplication and addition with division.

Equation 5.1

When multiplied by 2

$$n + \frac{n+1}{2}$$

$$2n+n+1$$

$$3n+1$$

Divide by 2 again

$$\frac{3n+1}{2}$$

Example 5.1

$$n=3$$

$$3 + \frac{3+1}{2} = 3 + 2 = 5$$

$$5 + \frac{5+1}{2} = 5 + 3 = 8$$

$$\frac{8}{2} = 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$$

Example 5.2

$$n=26$$

$$\frac{26}{2} = 13$$

$$13 + \frac{13+1}{2} = 13 + 7 = 20$$

$$\frac{20}{2} = 10$$

$$\frac{10}{2} = 5$$

$$5 + \frac{5+1}{2} = 5 + 3 = 8$$

$$\frac{8}{2} = 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$$

6-collatz on negative numbers.

If we want to give the negative number its value, we add its order in the negative as well.

Order of negative number $\frac{n-1}{2}$

Equation 6.1

$$n + \frac{n-1}{2} \quad \text{When multiplied by 2} \quad 2n+n-1$$

$$3n-1 \quad \text{Divide by 2 again}$$

$$\frac{3n-1}{2}$$

We can formulate the negative numbers in this form:

Theory6.1 (if we have a negative odd number, we add its order among the negative numbers, which is also negative, and if we have a negative even number, we divide it by 2. We repeat this process to finally reach $-4 \rightarrow -2 \rightarrow -1$).

Example6.1 $n=-3$ $-3 + \frac{-3-1}{2}$ $-3-2=-5$
 $-5-3=-8$ $\frac{-8}{2} = -4 \rightarrow -2 \rightarrow -1$

Example6.2 $n=-14$ $-7 + \frac{-7-1}{2}$ $-7-4=-11$
 $-11 + \frac{-11-1}{2} = -17$ $-17 + \frac{-17-1}{2} = -26$ $\frac{-26}{2} = -13$

$-13 + \frac{-13-1}{2} = -20$ $\frac{-20}{2} = -10$ $\frac{-10}{2} = -5$

$-5 + \frac{-5-1}{2} = -5 - 3 = -8$ $\frac{-8}{2} = -4 \rightarrow -2 \rightarrow -1$

7-Number Tracks Table.

we can predict the next step in the Collatz event.

Odd number + odd order = even number

$$1+1=2 \qquad 5+3=8 \qquad 9+5=14$$

Odd number + even order = odd number

$$3+2=5 \qquad 7+4=11 \qquad 11+6=17$$

Even-Odd	Odd-Even	Even-Even	Odd-Odd
1	3	5	7
9	11	13	15
17	19	21	23
25	27	29	31
33	35	37	39
41	43	45	47
49	51	53	55
57	59	61	63

8-References.

- Maddux, Cleborne D.; Johnson, D. Lamont (1997). *Logo: A Retrospective*. New York: Haworth Press. p. 160. [ISBN 0-7890-0374-0](#). The problem is also known by several other names, including: Ulam's conjecture, the Hailstone problem, the Syracuse problem, Kakutani's problem, Hasse's algorithm, and the Collatz problem.
- • Lagarias, Jeffrey C. (1985). "The $3x + 1$ problem and its generalizations". *The American Mathematical Monthly*. **92** (1): 3–23. [doi:10.1080/00029890.1985.11971528](#). [JSTOR 2322189](#).
- • According to Lagarias (1985),^[2] p. 4, the name "Syracuse problem" was proposed by Hasse in the 1950s, during a visit to [Syracuse University](#).
- • O'Connor, John J.; Robertson, Edmund F., "[Lothar Collatz](#)", [MacTutor History of Mathematics Archive](#), [University of St Andrews](#)